

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH:
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XORIJIY TAJRIBA**

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarning nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
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1-SHO‘BA. **ZAMONAVIY MARKETING KONSEPSIYASI** **ASOSIDA IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH**

APPLICATION OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES TO INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES: CURRENT SITUATION ANALYSIS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the current state of applying green technologies in industrial enterprises. It offers valuable insights into existing practices and explores the promising perspectives. Furthermore, the article proposes possible measures to support the application of green technologies in Uzbekistan.

Key words: green technologies, industrial enterprises, renewable energy, environmental impact, sustainability.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада саноат корхоналарида yashil texnologiyalarni қўллашнинг ҳозирги ҳолати ҳар томонлама tahlil қилинган. Мақолада joriy амалиёт ҳақида долзарб fikrlar taqdim этилган ва келгусидаги истиқболлар tahlil қилинган. Bundan tashqari, мақолада O'zbekistonda yashil технологиялардан фойдаланишни qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yuicha чора-тадбирлар таклиф этилади.

Калит сўзлар: yashil texnologiyalar, саноат корхоналари, қайта тикланадиган энергия манбалари, атроф-муҳитга таъсир, barqaror rivojlaniш.

Аннотация: В статье представлен комплексный анализ текущего состояния применения зеленых технологий на промышленных предприятиях. Она предлагает ценную информацию о существующих практиках и исследует перспективы их развития. Кроме того, в статье предлагаются возможные меры поддержки применения зеленых технологий в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: зеленые технологии, промышленные предприятия, возобновляемая энергия, воздействие на окружающую среду, устойчивость.

INTRODUCTION

The application of green technologies to industrial enterprises is a critical step towards achieving a sustainable future. Green technologies are those that reduce environmental impact and conserve resources. They can be applied to all aspects of industrial operations, from manufacturing processes to energy consumption to waste management.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in green technologies among industrial enterprises. This is due to a number of factors, including:

- Increased awareness of the environmental and economic costs of pollution and resource depletion.
- Government regulations and incentives to promote the use of green technologies.
- Technological advancements that have made green technologies more affordable and effective.

As a result of this growing interest, the application of green technologies to industrial enterprises is accelerating. This is having a positive impact on the environment, while also helping businesses to reduce costs and improve efficiency.

This article will provide a current situation analysis of the application of green technologies to industrial enterprises. It will also discuss the future perspectives of this field, and highlight some of the key challenges and opportunities that lie ahead.

Main part

Green technologies are becoming increasingly important in industrial enterprises, as companies seek to reduce their environmental impact and improve their resource efficiency.

There are a number of factors driving this trend, including (Figure 1):

- Government regulations: Governments around the world are implementing stricter environmental regulations, which is forcing businesses to adopt green technologies.
- Consumer demand: Consumers are becoming more environmentally conscious and are increasingly demanding products and services from companies that are committed to sustainability.

- Cost savings: Green technologies can help businesses to save money on energy and other resources [1].
- Some of the most common green technologies being used by industrial enterprises include:
- Renewable energy: Many companies are installing solar panels, wind turbines, and other renewable energy technologies to reduce their reliance on fossil fuels.

Figure 1. Factors driving the application of green technologies.

- Energy efficiency: Companies are also investing in energy-efficient equipment and processes to reduce their overall energy consumption.
- Water conservation: Companies are using water-efficient technologies and practices to reduce their water usage and wastewater discharge.
- Waste management: Companies are implementing waste reduction and recycling programs to minimize their environmental impact [2].

The application of green technologies to industrial enterprises is still in its early stages, but there is a growing trend towards adoption. It can be seen that mainly tech giants have defined their medium to long-term strategies regarding green technologies adoption.

Here are some examples of how industrial enterprises are using green technologies:

- Tesla: Tesla is a leading manufacturer of electric vehicles and solar panels. The company is helping to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by making it more affordable and convenient for people to switch to clean energy [3].
- Google: Google is committed to using 100% renewable energy by 2030. The company has installed solar panels and wind turbines on its campuses around the world. Google is also investing in energy-efficient technologies, such as data centers that use less water and energy [4].
- Walmart: Walmart is one of the largest retailers in the world. The company is working to reduce its environmental impact by investing in renewable energy, energy efficiency, and waste reduction programs. Walmart is also sourcing more sustainable products and selling them at lower prices [5].

These are just a few examples of how industrial enterprises are using green technologies to reduce their environmental impact and improve their resource efficiency. As green technologies become more affordable and efficient, we can expect to see their adoption continue to grow in the years to come.

Figure 2. Benefits of using green technologies in industrial enterprises.

There are several benefits to using green technologies in industrial enterprises (Figure 2):

- **Reduced environmental impact:** Green technologies can help businesses to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, and waste production. This can help to protect the environment and mitigate climate change.
- **Improved resource efficiency:** Green technologies can help businesses to use resources more efficiently, which can lead to cost savings.
- **Enhanced reputation:** Businesses that are seen as being environmentally friendly can enjoy a number of benefits, such as increased brand awareness, customer loyalty, and employee engagement.
- **Competitive advantage:** Green technologies can help businesses to gain a competitive advantage over their competitors. For example, businesses that are able to reduce their energy costs can offer lower prices to their customers.

So, why aren't green technologies widely available across industries? Because, there are also some challenges associated with using green technologies in industrial enterprises:

- **First of all, upfront costs:** Green technologies can be more expensive to purchase and install than traditional technologies. That's why most of the small and medium size enterprises find it very costly to transform their business activities towards green technologies. However, the long-term cost savings can be significant for them since more consumers are changing their mindsets towards green products globally.
- **Secondly, lack of expertise:** Some businesses may not have the expertise or resources to implement green technologies. Furthermore, it takes time to adopt "spillovers" from larger firms in terms of learning how to use and develop green technologies.

Figure 3. Challenges of using green technologies in industrial enterprises.

Thirdly, government regulations: Government regulations can be complex and can vary from one jurisdiction to another. This can make it difficult for businesses to comply with environmental regulations [6].

Despite these challenges, the benefits of using green technologies in industrial enterprises are clear. Businesses that adopt green technologies can reduce their environmental impact, improve their resource efficiency, and gain a competitive advantage.

In Uzbekistan, firms mainly face challenges due to their financial and skills constraints. Financial constraints can be divided into two groups. On the one hand, green technologies and innovations require high R&D costs to develop. Furthermore, as these kinds of inventions take place in advanced countries, adoption of these technologies are inaccessible for them.

The government of Uzbekistan has implemented several reforms to support private sector in green transformation processes. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a green economy until 2030" the main priority directions of the green transition were defined. One of the striking feature of this Decree is that the government supports the private sector in developing and adopting green technologies and innovations [7].

Moreover, the government has initiated to transform state-owned enterprises into more environment friendly production. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures directed to improve the environmental situation in selected industries, reducing the negative impact of waste on the environment and population health, effective usage of alternative energy sources" construction materials, metallurgical, chemical and textile industries will be transformed to green industries [8].

However, there are several issues regarding the green transition.

First, the appropriate indicators of green transition are not included in the national statistics system and the indicators reported by the relevant ministries and agencies are in an aggregate-level.

Second, the reforms are mainly focused on the adoption of green technologies from the frontier economies, not actually invention and development of innovations. So, it is a lot more expensive for the country and business representatives as well as this trend always requires continuously adoption of these technologies from abroad.

Furthermore, there is not such a skills development system in the field of green technologies in the country and research institutions and universities are financed to be equipped with technologies that are originally produced in advanced economies.

The government should focus on the following policy recommendations to further develop the sector and increase accountability and transparency as well as achieving sustainability in green transition:

- developing national indicators of green transition (macro and micro-level) and introducing a real-time reporting system;
- concentrating on the invention of green technologies rather than only adoption;
- investing on skills development. In this case, it is important to increase the responsibility and accountability of the personnel in the field.

CONCLUSION

The application of green technologies to industrial enterprises is growing rapidly, as more and more businesses recognize the benefits of reducing their environmental impact. Green technologies can help industrial enterprises to reduce energy consumption and costs, pollution and emissions, improve product quality and safety, enhance their reputation and brand image, attract and retain top talent as well as comply with environmental regulations.

The adoption of green technologies by industrial enterprises is being driven by a number of factors, such as increasing public awareness and demand for sustainable products and services, government regulations and incentives, technological advances and cost reductions.

The current situation of the application of green technologies to industrial enterprises is positive, with a growing number of businesses adopting these technologies and achieving significant benefits. However, there are still some challenges that need to be addressed, such as the high upfront cost of some green technologies and the lack of awareness and expertise among some businesses.

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